

Local Government in Poland

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Responsibilities and Public Services

2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Poland: An Introduction

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The Polish local self-government provides mainly a wide range of public services. Decentralization was a fundamental element of the Polish transformation and is a fundamental principle of the Polish political system. The self-government is responsible for satisfying the needs of the residents on an ongoing basis, including taking care of safety and public order. These tasks are allocated in accordance with the principle of subsidiarity. For example, as regards road maintenance: certain roads are the responsibility of the *gmina*, others of the *powiat*, then there are regional roads and finally roads for which the Polish State assumes responsibility. The same applies to tasks related to education, health care and social care. Moreover, it is very common to delegate state tasks to be performed by self-governments (so that they are performed as close to the citizens as possible).

In the years 1990-1999, there was a simple scheme of performing public tasks in Poland: responsibility was taken over either by the *gmina* self-government or by the Polish state (bodies and offices of delegated government administration). However, during political transformation further decentralization was given priority, so works on support for *gminas* in performing local tasks were in progress. In 1999, the *powiat* self-government was established (which includes several *gminas* in its territory). The *powiat*, as a larger self-government unit, took over the local tasks of a higher level (e.g. the *gmina* is responsible for primary schools, while the *powiat* is responsible for secondary schools). The number of *gminas* in one *powiat* ranges from 3 to 19.¹⁷

The exceptions are large urban *gminas* which due to their population and financial potential are able to handle higher-level tasks. They were granted the status of cities with *powiat* rights (one urban *gmina* (one city) corresponds to one *powiat*).

Therefore, *gmina* and *powiat* complement each other in order to provide services to the residents on an ongoing basis. However, the voivodeship self-government, established in 1999, is to play the role of a regional self-government, which has assumed some of the responsibility for the economic development of the regions from the state.

From the legal point of view, self-government units are to perform public tasks on their own behalf and on their own responsibility. Importantly, the law does not distinguish categories of tasks for urban or rural *gminas*. Self-governments may carry out these tasks independently,

¹⁷ Rady Ministrów, 'Obwieszczenie Prezesa Rady Ministrów z dnia 23 sierpnia 2017 r. w sprawie wykazu gmin i powiatów wchodzących w skład województw' (*ISAP M.P. 2017 poz. 853*, 7 September 2017) <<http://prawo.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/DocDetails.xsp?id=WMP20170000853>> accessed 1 July 2019.

entrusting tasks to other self-governments, cooperating with other self-governments. They can also privatize tasks or use the instrument of a public-private partnership.

As far as cooperation in performing tasks is concerned, there are 313 inter-communal unions in Poland. Common waste management is very popular – there are 70 such communal unions. The largest union consists of 27 *gminas*. In total, 683 *gminas* are members of a union whose objective is the common waste management, which accounts for 27.5 per cent of *gminas* in Poland¹⁸.

Another practice is to delegate local government tasks to other entities. The differences in operating strategies between urban and rural *gminas* can also be observed in this area.

A *gmina* self-government may assign the management of a small school (up to 70 students) under an agreement to a legal entity that is not a self-government unit (e.g. an association, a foundation) or to a natural person. This solution protects small rural communities against the liquidation of schools.

Tasks may be also carried out under a public-private partnership (e.g. running a sewage treatment plant (Konstancin-Jeziorna, Osina), building a local road (Łazy), building a school and a sports hall (Piaśtów)).

In Poland, PPPs are established very carefully. In the history of Poland, 135 such partnerships have been recorded to date. The majority of the partnerships involve *gminas* which entered into 84 such agreements in total (urban *gminas* 39, rural *gminas* 25, urban and rural *gminas* 20). However, due to the fact that some *gminas* entered into more than one partnership, only 57 *gminas* in Poland have experience with such a form of public service provision. It accounts for 2.3 per cent of all *gminas*¹⁹.

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¹⁸ Ministry of Internal Affairs and Administration, 'Zarejestruj, zmień statut lub wyrejestruj związek międzygminny, związek powiatów, związek powiatowo-gminny' (*Serwis Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej*, 2 July 2019)
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